

NOTES

Studies on some Anionic Complexes of Oxovanadium(IV)

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THE chemistry of oxovanadium(IV) is of interest from chemical, structural and biological point of view¹⁻⁵. Keeping this in view and our interest in the chemistry of mixed ligand complexes⁶⁻⁸, we report here the synthesis and characterisation of some mixed ligand anionic complexes of oxovanadium(IV) of the type $M[VOL_2X]$, where $M = Na$ or K ; $X = SCN^-$ or N_3^- ; $L =$ anion of acetylacetonate (acacH), oxine (oxH), pyridine carboxylic acid (pycaH).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. $VO(acac)_2$, $VO(ox)_2$ and $VO(pyca)_2$ were prepared by known methods¹⁰.

Preparation of complexes $K[VOL_2SCN]$: $VO(acac)_2$, $VO(ox)_2$, $VO(pyca)_2$ were reacted in ethanolic medium with KSCN in 1:1 molar ratio separately. The resulting solution was refluxed for 6h, the volume of the solution was reduced and kept overnight. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure.

The complexes $Na[VOL_2N_3]$ were prepared similarly by taking NaN_3 instead of KSCN.

Vanadium and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically by standard methods¹¹. Sodium and potassium were estimated using a Shimadzu AA.670

atomic absorption/flame emission spectrophotometer. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated using semi-micro methods. The complexes were characterised on the basis of ir spectra (KBr) in the range $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, electronic spectra (DMF), room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment, molar conductance and molecular weight (Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent) data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes confirm their stoichiometry as indicated in Table 1. The molecular weight data indicate the compounds as monomers. The complexes have high melting points ($> 250^\circ$). The molar conductance values of $65-70\ \Omega^{-1}$ ($10^{-3}M$ in DMF) for the complexes suggest them to be 1:1 electrolytes¹². The coordinating nature of SCN^- as revealed by conductance data is also supported by the ir spectral data. The room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment values of 1.78-1.80 B.M. are close to the spin-only values for one unpaired electron¹³.

In the acetylacetonate complexes, the ir bands due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=C}$ were observed at ~ 1570 and $\sim 1520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, respectively, indicating the presence of coordinated acetylacetonate (acac) as an uninegative bidentate ligand¹⁴. The presence of a strong band in oxinate complexes at $\sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O) indicates the presence of oxinate (ox) as uninegative ($N, \bar{O}$) bidentate ligand¹⁵. In the complexes containing pyridine carboxylic acid, the band due to free COOH group was absent; a new band due to $\nu_{as}\text{ COO}^-$ and pyridine ring was observed at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting coordination of picolinate as an uninegative ($N, \bar{O}$) bidentate ligand¹⁶. The thiocyanato complexes showed bands at ~ 2060 , ~ 820 and $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ν_{C-N} , ν_{C-S} and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL, DATA OF OXOVANADIUM COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Na/K	V	N	S		
$K[VO(acac)_2(SCN)]$	Greenish black	10.50 (10.77)	18.90 (14.07)	8.69 (8.86)	8.90 (8.84)	65	1.80
$Na[VO(acac)_2(N_3)]$	Dirty green	6.72 (6.97)	15.81 (15.48)	12.61 (12.72)	—	68	1.79
$K[VO(ox)_2(SCN)]$	Greenish black	8.40 (8.62)	11.19 (11.27)	9.15 (9.29)	6.95 (7.08)	67	1.78
$Na[VO(ox)_2(N_3)]$	Blackish	5.35 (5.47)	12.05 (12.19)	16.52 (16.66)	—	69	1.79
$K[VO(pyca)_2(SCN)]$	Dirty green	9.88 (9.56)	12.39 (12.48)	10.12 (10.29)	7.65 (7.84)	66	1.80
$Na[VO(pyca)_2(N_3)]$	Blue	5.99 (6.12)	13.48 (13.55)	18.02 (18.60)	—	70	1.78

δ_{NCS} modes, respectively, suggesting N-bonded thiocyanate ion¹⁷. The intense band at $\sim 2000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a weaker band at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively of azide ion were observed, indicating its terminal coordination¹⁸. The 950 cm^{-1} band was attributed to $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ ¹⁹. The coordination of thiocyanate and azide ion in the sixth coordination position lowers $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ from $\sim 990 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{VO}(\text{ox})_2$ and $\text{VO}(\text{pyca})_2$ to $\sim 950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present complexes. Lowering of the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ suggests coordination of thiocyanate and azide ion *trans* to V=O group in the complexes²⁰.

Electronic spectra of the complexes showed two bands, one transition is around 12000 cm^{-1} due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{zx} (ν_1) and the other around 16000 cm^{-1} due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ (ν_2).

The observed data are in conformity with a distorted octahedral structure²¹⁻²² for vanadium(IV).

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Precipitate based Selective Ion Sensitive Membrane Electrodes for Tripositive Chromium and Aluminium

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NO commercial ion selective electrode for Cr^{III} and Al^{III} ions is available. Both the ions are usually determined by indirect potentiometry in which a different electrode is used, e.g. copper(II) ISEs are being used¹ for the determination of Al^{III} . In this paper we report the electrodes for these tripositive ions which are based on the dithiozone precipitate of the respective ion as an electroactive material.

Experimental

Green coloured chromium(III) dithiozonate and ash coloured aluminium(III) dithiozenate precipitates were obtained by adding in dilute solutions of the salts of the respective metal ions, an ammonical solution of dithiozone². After washing and drying the precipitate, the master membrane with each precipitate was prepared by mixing the precipitate (100 mg) with epoxy resin (400 mg)³.

Preparation of electrodes: A small portion from each membrane was cut out and fixed at one end of the glass tube (o.d. 0.8 cm and i.d. 0.5 cm) with the help of Araldite. These tubes were filled with 0.1 M solution of CrCl_3 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, respectively. A saturated calomel electrode was inserted for electrical contact. A separate saturated calomel electrode was used as external reference electrode. The electrode systems can be represented as

SCE | 0.1 M $\text{M}^{\text{s}+}$ | membrane | sample | SCE

where, $\text{M} = \text{Cr}^{\text{s}+}$ or $\text{Al}^{\text{s}+}$. Before taking measurement the membrane of each electrode system was kept immersed for 6 days in 0.1 M solution of the respective ions.

Results and Discussion

Two separate sets of solution of CrCl_3 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ were prepared in which the concentration

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